

Transcription of Interview 2

*Shane Murphy
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Shane: ..National Health Insurance. There's four overarching questions.

Interviewee 2: Okay.

Shane: Our first question, rather broadly, is just, what are your views on the National Health Insurance?

Interviewee 2: [...] I've just looked at the overview of what government intended to achieve with the NHI. I'm of the view that it is a very good concept, that will, most definitely, benefit the poor, whereby it's unfortunate that the so-called middle class, or the people who are doing well, will help to [...]; but if you look at it from the overview perspective, it's something that, I'm of the view, that this country needs, and then it will, most definitely, benefit our people more, especially [...] who are the marginalised ones, who will benefit here, **nationally**, from the improved health system.

Shane: Okay. And what is your view on the funding? Or how do you think that the NHI should be funded?

Interviewee 2: The model that has been proposed, which, I'm not really familiar with it, but I'm of the view that it should be a funded from the tax payers funds, which will need prioritisation, on how we spend the [...]. [...] look at it, already, the Department of Health is allocated most of the budget within the province.

But from my perspective, the health of the people must not be subjected to the monetary ideal, but if you are **spending** the healthy people, all the people that can be [...] within a very short period of time, and then at the very convenient [...], **the funding wouldn't** be much of a problem. But what needs to be done, is that we'll need to look at governmental **spending** are, and then look at where can **you spend** money, as government. And in the areas where we'll identify the **servicing**, are those funds will need to be redirected to NHI.

Shane: Okay. And your views on the strategic purchasing, where they separate the provider from the funder, do you think that's a good idea? Or anything else you would think would work better?

Interviewee 2: That [...] on that, what was the [...] on that?

Shane: So the strategic purchasing is that the NHI would be an organ that is separate from state, as well as separate from private, so independent, and then they would purchase services from both public and private sectors.

Interviewee 2: I think **my** [...] that it will be independent, I think it will be a good idea, in **the sense** that the reality that our government, for some years, it has been surrounded by a number of corruption allegations and so forth, so if you are having an independent body, but which it, anyway, would be overseen by the [...], it would be a bit of a relief, because of even those people that will be [...], the issue

of corruption within our country is becoming a bigger issue. So if we are having an independent body, I think it might be a way, because of, it will not **have** much influence from **various** stakeholders, because it will be viewed as independent.

Shane: Okay. So you think that it's good, because it takes the opportunity for corruption away?

Interviewee 2: Yes.

Shane: And what are your views on working together with the private sector?

[04:48]

Interviewee 2: The issue that it is not only the possibility of government to provide services to the people, because of, as government, we are having a limited **responses**. But **by** [...] that they will be having the private health sector onboard, and having a collaboration here with them, I'm of the view that that is the best way to approach things. Not only the NHI, that [...] projects that have been [...] **access** for, if you look at most of the **PPP** agreement **where** we are having, the private / public partnership, I have the view that they've been working well; and then both [...] parties are able to have the benefits from the collaboration. So **by the** [...] that they will be having a similar model, which, of course, is not identical, but the issue that **we'll have the situation**, by the government, is playing its part, and also the private sector is coming onboard; so there will be a funding from both parties, with a view of benefiting the public at large, but not only one part.

Shane: Okay. And Mr Interviewee 2, in terms of your own engagement with government, have you been involved, or had interaction with the NHI policy development?

Interviewee 2: [...] I was following on the news, and various social medias, and I've seen the presentation which was done by, I think it was started by Dr Aaron Motsoaledi, whereby, even the new ministers [...] is taking it forward. But I've been following those developments, and I'm of the view that it's the way to go.

Shane: Okay. And so would you say that following the media, is how you get most of your information about the NHI?

Interviewee 2: Ja, that's where I got most of.. but with the media, I don't [...] the media, whereby someone will have written something about the NHI; I prefer listening at the engagement from the horse's mouth, which is an article, which will be informed by the interview that has been conducted by the Minister, the President, or the [...] **party** itself; but not the [...] of an individual.

Shane: Okay. And in the context of your managerial position, do you have any direct communication with government, on what the plan is, or how the implementation should go forward?

Interviewee 2: Not yet, because I must be honest, that I recently joined the Department of Health. I mean, from a complete different environment within the public sector; so I [...] **here, back in June**.

Shane: Okay. And then, what is your perception about the readiness of the current public health system, its current function, and to implement NHI?

Interviewee 2: I think what we will need to do, is that, I don't think we'll reach the stage where we are seeing the readiness is up to the top level. I'm of the view that there will need to **be** the cities or the provinces, where the NHI can be piloted, and see the benefit from that, and based on that piloting, then we can do the National **rollout**. But if we are looking at the issue of the readiness, there will always be exceptions that we are not **ready**, because of this and this.

So what we need to do, in order to implement the NHI, I'm of the view that we will need political will, and people who are going to take decisive decisions, irrespective of the readiness, because if you look at the issue of the readiness, we'll always have the **exceptions**, to say, we are not ready, no, we are not ready. When do we come to the issue of the readiness, **we will have clean forgotten about consent**. What we need to be looking at, is that, what did we intend to benefit, and who are the people who are going to benefit. But if you are looking at it from that perspective, [...] we are having a strong political will to implement it, it can be done.

[10:04]

Similarly to what has happened to the issue of **re-education**, there was political will, **in [...]** of the advices that were given, but if the country is of the view that this is the position that we need for our people, and it needs to be implemented as such.

Shane: And do you think that the political will is there, at the moment, to implement NHI?

Interviewee 2: The political will is there; I must say, that the issue that [...] **that [...]** - this is my [...], I must say, né? - **one thing** that the process to implement it, is being [...] **grew, we also** will need a **mass capital** to implement that. But if we were **growing**, and our GDP was growing at **acceptable** level, I'm of the view that it could have been implemented by now. But [...] **as you have asked for**, is mainly dependent on our economical **situation**, and then how our GDP is growing, which, at the end of the day, I think it **indicated** that we will need to fund this thing through that model.

So though the political will is there, but the economics situation is not really [...] **us now**; but I'm hopeful that, as a country, we will be able to grow our GDP, and our economy will be able **to grow**, with the view that, at the end of the day, we will implement the NHI.

Shane: Okay. You have mentioned the pilot projects, as well as corruption, or systems challenges, but what do you think are - apart from those - what do you think are the key challenges, to contracting and implementing NHI? And also, do you have any solutions for how it could be eased?

Interviewee 2: No, like I just indicated now, even beside the issue of the corruption, the manner in which our GDP is growing, and then how the [...] we, as a... **but not** as a country, the **world**, is in the unfortunate situation of **covid**, where most of the funding had to be redirected to other activities, that we cannot do away with, for now; so it became a bit of a challenge. But at the moment, until we are ready **again**, economic recovery **plan**, I think NHI, **it might not even take, as one will have one [...]** even looking at the [...].

Shane: Okay. And Mr Interviewee 2, how do you see your role in implementing NHI?

Interviewee 2: One of my role, it will be the **issue, because** NHI, it talks about more decentralisation of activities, whereby the services will, because even now, will have our district offices, where a number of activities might have been centralised here; but when we look at the NHI, the services will be decentralised, **when** actual services are being **tendered**. So my role, will be, as a financial manager, it will become decentralised [...] funds that we are having, and then how **do** we are making sure that [...] decentralise them, **they'll** work for the people which are intended for; and that the people on the ground are well-equipped to oversee the implementation. So I'm looking in, from the financial management point of view, from the issue of decentralisation of activities. That NHI will require the decentralisation of activities on the ground, so [...] **level**, whereby the people will receive services, as and when, it is required, without looking at the issue of bureaucracy of our [...] **skills**.

[15:10]

Shane: And Mr Interviewee 2, I know you say you only started half-way this year, but would you say that you feel that you have been empowered, as well as had the support, to do the implementation?

Interviewee 2: No, I'm saying, because of **whether** [...] **my** [...], **ability**, differently, because I had to look at the areas which were not doing well, and see to it, that **how can I turn** around things, and so forth. So the NHI, for now, it was not one of the **pilot**, but however, it's something that one will be actively participating on, looking at, in the **very near future**, which might even be the beginning of next year, in Jan.

Shane: Okay. Then, Mr Interviewee 2, my last question, just from your side, is there any other view or thought, that you would like to express?

Interviewee 2: No, beside that, I've indicated that I'm of the view that the NHI is a very good concept; I think, similarly to the one which, in the USA, that was introduced by the previous President there, Obamacare, the intention is very clear, that how do we have a healthy society, and sustain that, because if you're having a healthy society, and then it's where a number of activities will be able to grow, and so forth, and the people will be empowered. So I'm of the view that the NHI is a very good concept, that the government needs to implement, but what is making things to be difficult now, is the economic situation that we're sitting in, as a country.

Shane: Okay, perfect. Then, Mr Interviewee 2, that's all from my side. Thanks so much for your time and willingness, I really appreciate it, and your insight has added a lot of value.

Interviewee 2: Oh, thank you very much.

Shane: Alright, have a good day. Bye.